

Workshop report

Indicators of research integrity: an initial exploration of the landscape, opportunities and challenges

Prepared on behalf of UK Research and Innovation, Cancer Research UK and GuildHE

July 2022

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Indicators of research integrity: an initial exploration of the landscape, opportunities and challenges

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SECTION ONE

Introduction

1.1 Background

UK Research and Innovation, Cancer Research UK and GuildHE are leading efforts to investigate potential indicators of research integrity. Their work builds on the principles and commitments in the [UK Concordat to Support Research Integrity](#) and aims to explore indicators that could help research organisations, funders of research and research infrastructures, researchers, publishers and others to identify and promote high levels of research integrity.

Research Consulting was commissioned to undertake a preliminary exploration of the topic between November 2021 and May 2022, with findings summarised in a discussion document available to download via the [Zenodo repository](#). The present document provides a summary of a workshop focusing on the discussion document and aiming to provide insights into possible next steps in this project.

To better contextualise the issues discussed in this workshop summary report, it is recommended that the discussion document is read first. Anonymised quotes from participants are included throughout this document to illustrate some of the points discussed.

1.2 The online workshop

On 26 April 2022, the project sponsors and Research Consulting hosted an online workshop for a broad range of stakeholder representatives, on the topic of research integrity indicators. Invited participants included a mix of research funding organisations, research performing organisations, publishers, learned societies, sector organisations and researchers, including at different levels of seniority. In total, 28 representatives of these stakeholder groups attended the workshop (Appendix A), with 26 being from the UK, one from the USA and one from Ireland.

The event aimed to achieve a greater understanding of:

- the levels of acceptance of potential purposes of indicators;

- the perceived roles and responsibilities of funders, research performing organisations, publishers and researchers, including how indicators might be governed; and
- the challenges and/or sensitivities at a more granular level, across the full diversity of the research ecosystem, including for example discipline areas, research methodologies, research organisation types and scales of operation, and career stages of researchers.

As part of the above, the workshop also sought to scope out inclusion/exclusion criteria and priorities for further work on research integrity indicators, including in relation to equality, diversity and inclusion, bullying and harassment, and research culture and environment.

1.3 Approach

The workshop lasted for three hours and started with a summary of the above-mentioned discussion document; this was followed by a plenary session seeking to address any feedback and immediate reactions to the discussion document. During the remainder of the workshop, participants contributed via a mix of plenary and breakout sessions, including the use of Mentimeter (an interactive tool) and the meeting chat.

Participants were split by the organisers into three pre-set breakout rooms, each including a balanced selection of representatives of different stakeholder groups. Breakout sessions were moderated by dedicated chairs (Ian Carter – Carter Research Navigation; Laura Fortunato – University of Oxford; Rob Johnson – Research Consulting), who were then tasked with summarising the separate breakout discussions during plenary sessions.

Participants were encouraged to comment on the discussions had in other breakout rooms, to enable an additional level of sharing and ideation.

1.4 Definitions

In our discussion document, indicators were defined as quantitative or qualitative factors providing a means to measure achievement, to reflect changes, or to help assess the performance or state of play. This definition included both lagging indicators, which can help measure progress or performance against a baseline, and leading indicators, which can help measure practices and behaviours that are, in theory, expected to lead to change or performance in the future.

During the workshop, examples of indicators were provided to participants, with the understanding that these were only illustrative:

- Quantitative indicators
 - What is the annual level of investment for activities supporting research integrity? [£]
 - What proportion of reported cases of misconduct have led to corrective action? [%]
- Qualitative indicators

- How does the organisation liaise with staff to inform the design, rollout, ongoing support and periodic revision of integrity policies/systems?
- What training and educational resources are available to members of the ethical review committee?
- Binary indicators
 - Does the organisation have a named contact for research integrity? [Yes/No]
 - Does the organisation have a clear procedure to protect whistle-blowers? [Yes/No]

A mind map summarising the facets of research integrity was also provided during the event, based on a more detailed chart available in our discussion document (see Figure 1).

1.5 Acknowledgements

We gratefully acknowledge the input from workshop participants (see Appendix A), moderators and the project sponsors, whose insights have contributed to the finished text of this workshop summary report.

Figure 1. Mind map of facets of research integrity.

SECTION TWO

Scope of indicators

2.1 Scope of research integrity

Participants were quick to acknowledge that “research integrity” is difficult to define, even with the strong direction provided by the UK Concordat. This issue arises from the broad range of stakeholders with an involvement in this area and their individual perspectives, but also from differences in organisational size and disciplinary focus. As a result, there is a tension between the desire for a shared definition of research integrity, which would facilitate the creation of common indicators, and the recognition that it inevitably has many different facets (see Figure 1) and must consider different perspectives. It was acknowledged that the UK Concordat operates alongside *other concordats, agreements and frameworks*, which would naturally be affected (to varying extents) should a framework of research integrity indicators be introduced. In particular, the workshop explored the implications of separating research integrity from the parallel topics of research culture, equality, diversity and inclusion, and bullying and harassment. The difficulty (and danger) of artificially separating research integrity from research culture became apparent in the discussion, for example because indicators may shift from covering integrity as intended in the UK Concordat to describing more limited concepts such as rigour or research quality (and therefore allowing only limited coverage of facets around ‘Care and respect’, see Figure 1). However, it was also noted that considering both at the same time may lead to too broad a conversation that inhibits meaningful progress.

2.2 Value of indicators

Early on in our discussion, there was clear agreement that, before creating indicators, one would need to carefully consider what problems any indicators are trying to address. This has a dual purpose: (i) by identifying specific use cases for indicators, future efforts can be focused on what *should* be measured as opposed to what *could* be measured; and (ii) engagement and acceptance from the community

can be gained. Participants noted that good indicators would enable stakeholders in the research landscape and beyond to be confident in the value of the research conducted and shared. This gives rise to an important point: there is a potential difference between actors (e.g. research performing organisations, researchers, research funders, publishers) and observers/users (e.g. regulators, the public, research users) in the nature of their understanding and potential use of indicators – something that any further thinking in this domain should acknowledge. For example, for observers and users, the indicators may be more about creating and maintaining trust in the research, whereas for actors in the research system they will also be about identifying areas for change.

Overall, participants noted that indicators should not be created for their own sake, and there was broad agreement that they should be formative rather than performative. For example, should a researcher’s work give rise to concerns in terms of research integrity, they should be supported in learning from these rather than immediately punished with sanctions. Finally, it was noted that indicators may also help organisations identify areas for additional support or training with regard to research integrity.

“We have to accept that indicators that we might design for formative purposes, could down the line be used by other stakeholders for punitive purposes.”

2.3 Purposes of indicators

Our discussion document hypothesised four potential purposes for research integrity indicators:

1. understanding, planning and evaluating interventions that aim to improve the research environment, the integrity and the overall quality of research;
2. assessing whether research(er) practices and behaviours are in line with organisational expectations around research integrity;

3. identifying systemic pressures affecting research integrity, and harnessing opportunities for change among different stakeholder groups; and
4. enabling (meta)researchers to reference an agreed framework for evidence around research integrity.

Participants were asked whether any of the above purposes are appropriate, and they broadly agreed that, before seeing any actual set of indicators, it would be difficult to provide an in-depth and well considered response. Nevertheless, it appears that the least controversial purpose would be to understand, plan and evaluate interventions (#1 above): although not a definitive finding, this is in line with the suggestion that next steps should consider macro level indicators rather than ones focused on individuals (see section 3). In this context, participants from publishing houses also noted that their role with regard to research integrity was not fully reflected, and that next stages of this work would benefit from a clearer discussion in this direction (see section 3).

2.4 Organisational and disciplinary variation

As noted above, research integrity will have different meanings based on context. In particular, what is good practice and what success might look like are very likely to differ across disciplines and types of organisations. For example, participants noted that the least feasible facets (see Figure 1) may be the most important ones in certain disciplines, and the risk of translating indicators from one discipline into another was also highlighted.

“It is important to recognise the diversity of settings where research takes place but not to generalise indicators to a stage where they become meaningless.”

Expectations around research integrity were also described as varying based on one’s career stage. This is not to imply that there are cases where failures of integrity are acceptable, but simply that some may make mistakes in light of more limited training or awareness of academic or disciplinary standards.

To address organisational and disciplinary variation, a participant noted that it might be useful to map out how different indicators may apply in different contexts, for example by developing use cases. Doing

so could illustrate the distinctions in reach and significance of practices between, for example, an individual researcher, someone leading a team of researchers, an organisational research leader, a reviewer, an editor, a managing editor, a programme manager or a funding director.

2.5 Prioritising indicators for future work

The facets of research integrity may be prioritised based on different principles or criteria to then create indicators. There was agreement that a balance should be achieved between feasibility and ensuring that indicators describe a range of phenomena relevant to the discussion. For example, one could consider quantitative measures of open sharing behaviours – highly feasible yet of partial relevance – as well as indicators providing a more nuanced picture of alignment with good research practices in a given discipline – far more difficult to measure but closely related with potential failures of research integrity.

Key Takeaways

- Research integrity has no broadly accepted definition at the international level, but the UK Concordat to Support Research Integrity provides a useful framework for reflection. What is good practice and what success might look like are very likely to differ across both disciplines and types of organisations
- It is risky to artificially split research integrity from parallel topics such as research culture, but considering both at the same time is complex. It is important to avoid duplication and foster connectivity with other initiatives.
- Good indicators would enable increased confidence in research, although there is a difference in perspectives between research actors and external observers and users.
- Indicators should have a formative focus and should not be created for their own sake: they should support a research system that enables researchers to grow and improve.
- The prioritisation of indicators must balance measuring the phenomena that matter the most against what’s feasible to measure.

SECTION THREE

Practical considerations

3.1 Levels of indicators

Participants noted that the creation of research integrity indicators would give rise to a wide range of practical questions. Further developing the analysis in the discussion document into specific measures would, for example, led to questions such as: To what type(s) of organisations does an indicator apply? At what levels of aggregation is the indicator meaningful? (e.g. by discipline, by organisation, by country).

Thinking along these lines also made participants wonder whether macro level indicators focusing on the big picture should be applied to lower levels (i.e. meso or micro) or if it is better to start from micro level indicators and aggregate them to build an overall picture of the landscape. The latter option may yield results that reflect real practices, but it is also obvious that gathering information at the micro level (e.g. individual researchers, research groups) is much more complex and sensitive than gathering insights from the central administration of research performing organisations, funders or publishers.

Naturally, there is also an option to collect indicators at the macro level and only consider them to describe macro level trends, with no drill down or implication that they may apply to organisations or individuals: this is likely to encounter the least resistance from research stakeholders, but it will be important to verify whether such an approach would yield actionable insights.

“Are we talking about national indicators, or organisational, or right down to more granular levels such as departments or research groups, or even down to individuals? I think that’s an important axis to consider, including when thinking about feasibility.”

3.2 Managing organisational and individual pressures

It was discussed that the use of indicators can lead to negative effects for institutions and individuals,

particularly in the form of increased pressures to achieve set targets or perform better than other organisations or peers. This is what often leads to the breakdown of indicator frameworks, whereby the intended impact is shadowed by misaligned behaviours and phenomena such as gaming. For example, participants noted that pressures on institutions are known to trickle down to the researcher level, leading to negative consequences at multiple levels.

As a result, it was recommended that a reward-based mechanism is considered to drive positive change and minimise burdens on organisational support systems. In this context, it was also noted that compliance-driven approaches should be avoided.

“Issues in research culture, which I think is the best overall term for what we’re looking at, often derive from misaligned priorities or incentives.”

3.3 Roles and responsibilities

Throughout the workshop, it was made clear that contributions from different stakeholder groups will be key for the successful development and deployment of a research integrity indicators framework. The following observations were made with regard to possible roles and responsibilities:

- Individual researchers are generally considered as the primary stakeholder with regard to research integrity indicators, as their individual and collective behaviours are what is ultimately being measured. A desire was expressed to achieve a research system where researchers do not feel that they have to choose between what is best for research and what is best for their career progression.
- Research performing organisations are well-placed to foster engagement with academic communities, including individuals and different subject areas and to ensure that indicators are in line with researcher practices. Research performing

organisations are also responsible for providing training and for raising awareness around research integrity, which may potentially include indicators.

- Funders were described as having both interests (e.g. monitoring the efforts of those they fund) and responsibilities (e.g. positively influencing research stakeholders via grant conditions, developing effective policies, being accountable to their stakeholders). However, they are not as close as research performing organisations or publishers to the data that would inform indicators.
- Learned societies are seen as having a prominent position to help understand disciplinary variation in good practices, with those that act as professional standards bodies having special relevance in areas where they exist.
- Publisher roles are not fully reflected in the current UK Concordat, which may in part be due to their limited role in the formation of the document. Yet, their contribution to fostering a research system where integrity is prioritised is critically important (e.g. via peer review and information held in their submission systems), and their role in setting expectations is significant (e.g. via reporting standards and author requirements).

"I don't see a role for funders in the creation and collection of detailed data. We really want to avoid duplicating information across the sector."

Overall, it appeared clear that guidance for all stakeholders involved in a research integrity indicators framework should be co-created and made available to support all phases, from data collection all the way through to the assessment of the framework itself.

3.4 Data to inform indicators

The above discussion around roles and responsibilities led to important considerations around data, including who provides source information for indicators, who calculates them, maintains them and assesses them. Publishers were described as a likely data provider, but it was also acknowledged that data on research integrity is not consistently collected, held and shared. It was suggested that the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE) might operate as an intermediary in future discussions, potentially playing a coordinating role for publishers.

Research performing organisations are also likely to be data providers in the long term, potentially building on the annual research integrity statements they currently produce. However, the topic of bureaucratic burdens was raised multiple times during the workshop.

"If the data behind the indicators was made available to (meta)researchers, then they could explore the biases and the way that the indicators are shifting the system itself."

From the perspective of digital infrastructure, a participant noted that it will be essential to develop sustainable and efficient data assets that can ensure there is a reduction in bureaucracy. Notably, it was also mentioned that this is only possible if a somewhat formal indicators framework is in place first, as this would affect the requirements for any underpinning infrastructure. Another important point raised around data is that indicators should ideally be accompanied by an open dataset, although an extent of anonymisation may be needed (or, alternatively, a form of secure storage and access). This type of technical infrastructure is certainly within reach, but one should also acknowledge the effort and costs involved in designing a suitable solution. Existing players in the research infrastructure space (such as Jisc in a UK context) may play a role in enabling the exchange of information between publishers, institutions and other relevant stakeholders.

Key Takeaways

- Indicators may, in principle, apply at different levels. Their application, aggregation or disaggregation will only be meaningful in some cases, and this needs further discussion.
- Indicators should be designed to minimise negative effects, particularly pressures on institutions and individuals. Indicators should not be compliance-driven, to avoid issues such as misaligned behaviours and gaming.
- All research stakeholders have a stake in the creation of integrity indicators, whether as subjects, users or data providers. Engagement across the research community is essential.
- The data to inform indicators needs to be sourced sustainably, minimising burdens.

SECTION FOUR

Making progress

4.1 Planning next steps

Views were somewhat split between (i) a desire to just try and create some trial indicators; and (ii) the need to not rush next steps. Either way, the keyword is 'engagement': no indicators will be acceptable unless a broad set of stakeholder voices are heard. Such engagement will also enable well-informed prototype use cases to be created and for future efforts to be better focused.

"One of my biggest fears when it comes to this is a lack of focus, whereby indicators become a tick box exercise where various organisations compete on fulfilling that tick box and losing sight of the main intentions around research integrity."

Table 1 provides an overview of Dos and Don'ts shared during the workshop, including the suggestion to create a working group tasked with further exploring this evolving area. As discussed during the event, the idea of a working group focusing on research integrity indicators may well overlap with or support future activities of the UK Committee for Research Integrity, and this may provide a useful and authoritative platform for further community engagement and practical progress.

"A working group sounds like a good idea. But I agree with the point that it needs to involve the co creation of forms of engagement that reach deeply, respectfully and authentically into the communities concerned."

Participants recommended that a pilot set of indicators should not focus on the micro level (e.g. department, individual), as this would lead to complex roadblocks too soon in the process. A focus on the macro level (which is in line with the UK Concordat) is seen as preferable, although it may require some generalisations and an extent of oversimplification as a starting point.

Table 1. Dos and Don'ts of research integrity indicators.

What to consider

- Creating a working group embedded in relevant communities, to continue the exploration started with the present project
- Keeping people involved in a dynamic process of co-creation
- Building a range of prototype use cases for indicators across different disciplines and institutions
- Looking at existing data and piloting its potential reuse to inform indicators
- Building on facets and phenomena that can be measured but also considering ones that are deemed to be important yet difficult to measure
- Involving the public and other research users, as appropriate
- Taking a phased approach

What to avoid

- Rushing the process
- Creating simplistic approaches, including a narrow set of indicators only based on low-hanging fruit
- Imposing top-down and/or compliance-driven indicators that may lead to gaming or misalignment
- Designing approaches that unduly increase burdens
- Designing indicators that only apply to a subset of disciplines or organisation types

4.2 Conclusions

The workshop enabled knowledge-sharing between experts across the research integrity landscape and showcased significant enthusiasm and interest from the community. A range of observations shared during the workshop should be considered to inform future developments:

1. **Clarity is needed around the purpose of indicators:** In this regard, the community should consider indicators that are formative and facilitate good practice rather than punitive or compliance-driven.
2. **A research integrity indicators framework should be co-created and co-owned by the community:** Further efforts should be bottom-up and based on

broad engagement, with coordination from relevant sector bodies.

3. **The heterogeneity of the sector should be fully acknowledged when creating indicators:** There is a keen interest in the level at and extent to which indicators could be viably used. This includes the structural level of the analysis (e.g. from individual to country level); the focus of each indicators (e.g. indicators about the research environment vs indicators about behaviours); and applicability across a range of organisations of different size, different disciplinary mixes and levels of seniority.
4. **A research integrity indicators framework should not unduly add bureaucracy for research performing organisations, research funders, publishers or any other potential data providers:** Any relevant quantitative data available today

should be considered as an input to a research integrity indicators framework, with the understanding that contextual information may be needed to complement this. This means identifying existing data and making the best of it before seeking to collect more.

Overall, participants expressed strong support for continued exploration of research integrity indicators.

If the above observations from this expert gathering are embraced, there is potential for this productive conversation to continue and lead to the long-term objective of creating indicators that are aligned with the UK Concordat to Support Research Integrity, follow good practice principles and are acceptable and transparent, whilst also minimising burdens for those involved.

Appendix A. Participants

The following stakeholders contributed to our workshop and their input is gratefully acknowledged.

Table A1. Workshop participants (listed in alphabetical order).

Name	Organisation	Role
Ali Alshukry	University of Nottingham	Head of Research Integrity
Tanita Casci	University of Oxford	Director, Research Strategy & Policy Unit
Vanessa Cuthill	British Academy	Director of Research
Ben Dickinson	Hindawi	Research Integrity Manager
Andy Dixon	University of Portsmouth	Deputy Director (Environment and Strategy)
Stephen Farrier	Royal Central School of Speech and Drama	Reader in Theatre and Performance
Andrew George	UK Committee on Research Integrity	Co-chair
Rachael Goberman-Hill	UK Committee on Research Integrity	Co-chair
Chris Graf	Springer Nature	Research Integrity Director
Zoe Hammatt	-	Independent consultant
Steven Hill	Research England, The UK Forum for Responsible Research Metrics	Director of Research
Maura Hiney	Health Research Board Ireland	Head of International Cooperation, Evaluation and Targeted Programmes
Neil Jacobs	UK Reproducibility Network	Head of the UKRN Open Research Programme
Alison Lloyd	Manchester Metropolitan University	Research Ethics and Governance Manager
Malcolm Macleod	University of Edinburgh / UK Reproducibility Network	Professor of Neurology and Translational Neuroscience, Academic Lead for Research Improvement and Research Integrity
Catriona Maccallum	Hindawi	Director of Open Science
Richard Malham	University of St Andrews	Head of Research Policy, Integrity and Governance
Hazel McGraw	Scottish Funding Council	Senior Policy Analysis Officer
Victoria Moody	Jisc	Director of research and innovation sector strategy
Jonathan Morris	Royal Historical Society	Vice-President & Chair of the Research Policy Committee
Alis Oancea	University of Oxford	Professor of Philosophy of Education and Research Policy
Verity Postlethwaite	SOAS, University of London	Research Associate
Rachel Safer	Oxford University Press	Senior Publisher
Karen Stroobants	Royal Society of Chemistry	Policy Adviser
Anne Taylor	Wellcome	Head of Grants Operations
Daniel Wake	Universities UK	Policy Manager
Sally Wilson	Emerald	Publishing Director
Xin Xu	University of Oxford	Research Fellow

Thank you for reading

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Cancer Research UK is the largest charitable funder of cancer research in the world, funding around 50% of all publicly funded cancer research here in the UK. We want to accelerate progress and see 3 in 4 people surviving their cancer by 2034. Cancer Research UK supports research into the prevention, detection and treatment of cancer through the work of over 4,000 scientists, doctors and nurses. Our research strategy is underpinned by our principles: to invest in creative people who can deliver research of the highest quality, to support research to reduce cancer inequalities and improve outcomes for everyone, and to involve people affected by cancer in our work.

GuildHE is an officially recognised representative body for UK higher education. Our members include universities, university colleges, further education colleges and specialist institutions from both the traditional and private (“not for profit” and “for profit”) sectors. Through our dedicated research consortium, GuildHE Research, we engage the full diversity of our institutions, people, and places in research and innovation, and advocate for the recognition and support of excellent research wherever it is found. We help our members to embed a positive and constructive research culture, develop robust research and innovation strategies, and establish appropriate infrastructure through which they can drive forward their ambitions.

UK Research and Innovation works in partnership with universities, research organisations, businesses, charities, and government to create the best possible environment for research and innovation to flourish. As the UK’s largest public funder of research and innovation it is our responsibility to ensure the health of the system as a whole, now and in the future. As a steward of this system, we work together with our many partners to benefit everyone through knowledge, talent and ideas. Operating across the whole of the UK with a combined budget of more than £7 billion, UK Research and Innovation brings together the seven research councils, Innovate UK and Research England.

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